

Leveraging AI for Enhanced Student Productivity: A Case Study of Cubbes Student Information System in Nigerian Universities

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The purpose of this study is to leverage Artificial Intelligence (AI) for enhanced student productivity in Nigerian universities, using Cubbes SIS as a case study. Cubbes functions as a digital assistant, equipped with learning content, past questions, and peer networking capabilities. The application integrates AI to automate and enhance decision-making and personalize student experience. A mixed methodology of quantitative and qualitative methods was used to evaluate the efficiency of Cubbes using download counts, active sessions, and feature usage. Additionally, an online survey consisting of qualitative insights from open-ended responses was carried out. 184 students across 170 universities were selected using a stratified random sampling technique. Data were analysed using Mean, Standard Deviation, Independent Samples t-Test and NVivo. The findings suggested that AI integration into SIS can significantly improve data transmission, learning outcomes, and institutional responsiveness to students' needs. This initiative aligns with the Core Curriculum Minimum Academic Standards (CCMAS) e-Learning policy. The result of the study on Engagement: Mean = 3.7 (SD = 0.9) with an average of 3.4 sessions per week per user, with spikes during exam periods; Personalization of Content: Mean = 4.0 (SD = 0.7); Trust in Security & Authentication: Mean = 3.7 (SD = 0.9). The study concludes that an AI-powered SIS such as Cubbes can bridge performance gaps, improve operational efficiency, and redefine student engagement across universities in Nigeria.

Keywords:
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Introduction

The way universities manage student information worldwide has drastically changed and evolved with the advent of technology. Digital solutions such as the Student Information System (SIS) ease the complexities of managing academic and administrative tasks in the university system (Zhang, 2025; Simelane-Mnisi & Mthimunye, 2025). While some schools rely on custom-developed portals to manage course content, course enrollment, exam registration, payments, etc., others use open-source LMS such as Moodle. According to Laudon and Laudon (2018), an information system is a set of interrelated components that collect, process, store, and distribute information to

support decision-making and control in an organization. In the education ecosystem, SIS offers students, administrators, and executives analyzed data for decision-making and coordination (Bhosale & Jamsandekar, 2022). Alumona and Akinseinde (2023) describe LMS as a server-based or cloud-based software program that stores information about users and course materials and enables learning to take place without constraints of time and space. With the advent of technological developments, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been used to provide customized teaching solutions based on big data and algorithmic analysis to understand students' individual educational needs (Wu,

2024). Laudon and Laudon (2018, p. 619) define AI as an effort to develop computer-based systems that can behave like humans with the ability to learn languages. Through personalized learning plans and teaching methods, AI can better meet students' interests and needs and stimulate the interest and motivation for learning (Wu, 2024). These systems, enabled by advances in AI, offer capabilities to personalize learning through the real-time analysis of student performance and adaptive content recommendations (Villegas-Ch et al., 2025).

One of the primary functions of SIS is to avail students with a digitized copy of the learning course material. In fact, according to the Nigerian National Policy on Education (NPE) on guidelines for open and distance learning in Nigerian universities, the use of ICT is a benchmark for quality assurance in ensuring that learning is interactive, comprehensive, accessible, contemporary, and learner friendly (NUC, 2025). Given the rapidly changing landscape of the sector, universities will need to reinvent themselves into organizations that can adapt quickly and flourish in a constantly evolving globalized environment. Thus, universities can no longer afford to be static in their updates of learning materials. Under the recently designed national curriculum of Nigeria, the Core Curriculum Minimum Academic Standard (CCMAS), 30 percent of the learning content in each of the programmes would be developed by the individual universities, the rest 70 percent of the core course would be delivered on a national basis (NUC-CCMAS, 2023). Introduction of blended learning in curriculum delivery is another significant aspect of the CCMAS (Saliu, 2023). Another major feature of the CCMAS is the introduction of blended learning in the delivery of the curriculum (Saliu, 2023). By

this approach, universities are encouraged to imbue conventional face-to-face classroom instruction with online learning experiences, where electronic copies of the curriculum, course material, and other digital tools are made available to enhance learning.

The AI-based SIS integrates big data analysis, cloud computing and mobile Internet technologies to automate student information processing, reduce manual errors, and improve management efficiency and accuracy (Villegas-Ch et al., 2025). With the assistance of intelligent analysis tools and database APIs, the system can deeply understand students' needs, realise personalised teaching and fine management, and ensure multi-platform and multi-terminal access, so as to achieve the purpose of information accessibility anytime and anywhere (Zhang, 2025). In the development of SIS, relevant resources like course content, previous questions, CCMAS, images, audio, and video recordings that are fed into the system are categorised as unstructured data. Unstructured data is not pre-defined and is often hard to search, and makes up 80 percent of big data, according to Altexsoft (2020). Because unstructured data does not include schemas, tables, dimensions, etc., they have often been ignored in the past because there is no real way to make analyses. However, with the advent of new technologies like artificial intelligence, machine learning, and advanced analytics, data analysis can be done on unstructured data (Altexsoft, 2020). Finally, AI enhances the performance of an SIS by automating the students' academic life and extra-curricular activities (Manal et al., 2025; Zhang, 2025). According to Qian et al. (2025), this could result in a better study-life balance and thereby produce efficient graduates. Reminders and prompt features keep students on top of their schedule at all times (Manal et al., 2025). The application of

AI algorithms to a database of course content and previous questions intelligently learns and optimises student performance through a recursive feedback loop (Lin et al., 2023). Many students appreciate the role of AI in providing timely formative feedback and enabling large-scale teaching operations through automated grading systems (Wang et al., 2024).

Although higher education has benefited from the technological advancements, existing SIS and LMS are inflexible and narrow in scope (Alumona & Akinseinde, 2023; Qian et al., 2025). Simelane-Mnisi & Mthimunya (2025) argued that the current applications are fragmented, cumbersome and not personalised, which makes them less effective in assisting students' academic productivity. Alumona and Akinseinde (2023) went on to add that the LMS like Moodle is mostly designed and populated by the university staff or administrator, thereby putting the students at a disadvantage by limiting their active involvement and control over their academic and extra-curricular activities. Another challenge is interoperability and student engagement with the course content in existing SIS and LMSes. While the CCMAS encourages blended learning and flexibility in curriculum delivery, there is still a lack of institutional alignment (Okenema, 2025). Following the aftermath of the COVID-19 outbreak, the National Universities Commission (NUC) issued guidelines for e-Learning in which universities are expected to facilitate learner autonomy and self-paced learning through flexible, interactive content using blended approaches (NUC, 2023). Empirical studies on digitization and CCMAS compliance for better learning experience in Bayelsa State, Nigeria revealed that even with CCMAS compliance, lack of digital infrastructure, poor

connectivity and low digital skills among users still pose a threat to full adoption of blended learning reforms (Okenema, 2025). Alumona and Akinseinde (2023) also reported that the actual level of LMS implementation in Delta State tertiary institutions was low and that both staff and students reported that major factors militating against adoption were weak online teaching infrastructure and low ICT proficiency. While AI has the potential to revolutionize learning through personalized learning, predictive analytics and automating mundane academic tasks, it is still in its early stages of integration into SIS (Swathieswari & Shanmugavadivu, 2025). Furthermore, there are significant gaps in ensuring long-term student engagement, data privacy, interoperability with course materials, LMS, and third-party applications within the existing SIS architecture (Wang et al., 2024). As a result, students are left with systems that are transactional rather than transformational in their approach to the academic journey. Without an AI-powered SIS that addresses these shortcomings, Nigerian universities risk not complying with the NUC CCMAS e-Learning guidelines while students miss out on the opportunity to leverage AI to improve their productivity on academic and extracurricular activities.

Research Questions

To address these gaps, two research questions were raised:

1. What impact does Cubbes SIS have on enhancing student engagement and personalized learning experience?
2. How do students and educators address data privacy and algorithm biases in use of AI-powered SIS

Aim of this Study

The aim of this study is to leverage AI for enhanced student productivity in Nigerian

universities, using Cubbes, an AI-Powered SIS as case study.

Objectives of this Study

The objectives were to:

1. identify how Cubbes enhances student engagement.
2. identify how Cubbes facilitates the development of personalized learning experiences.
3. assess how Cubbes addresses data privacy, security, and algorithmic bias in an AI-powered SIS environment.
4. examine how Cubbes addresses challenges of interoperability between SIS/LMS platforms and other third-party applications.

Literature Review

Research has highlighted the exploration of AI in education, particularly in personalized learning settings, sustained engagement, enhance teaching efficiency and learning outcomes, among others (Wang et al, 2023). Yuskovych-Zhukovska et al. (2022) explored opportunities in the integration of AI and digital technologies within education and SIS. Similarly, Zhang (2025) emphasized how AI-driven information management systems in universities can support quality monitoring and decision-making. His work shows that data mining techniques, such as association rules and apriori algorithm, can significantly improve both learning support and institutional efficiency. In addition to institutional management, Villegas-Ch et al. (2025) introduced an AI-based intelligent tutoring system capable of delivering adaptive and personalized feedback. While Wang et al described engagement, a key feature of an AI-Powered SIS, as the level of active participation and involvement in educational activities, reflected in students' interactions, feedback, and interest in the learning process.

Their findings demonstrated notable improvements in undergraduate Programming and Mathematics performance with positive student perceptions, thereby showcasing AI's transformative potential in STEM education. Complementing this, Karoglou et al. (2025) presented the Higher Education Class for the Future (HECOF) Project, which combined AI and immersive environments to create adaptive Engineering education experiences to provides sustained engagement and personalized learning. Their study confirmed positive learning outcomes and high levels of student satisfaction, although the improvements varied across individuals.

Despite these advancements, several studies have identified barriers that limit adoption. Yuskovych-Zhukovska et al. (2022) explored the risks of AI in education, highlighting limitations of algorithm biases and data privacy. Chen et al. (2022a) identified a reluctance among instructors to embrace AI tools, partly due to data security and storage concerns. Akgun and Greenhow (2022) cautioned students and educators must be cognizant of ethical concerns, including data privacy, algorithm bias, transparency, and accountability. Research from Wang et al. (2023) reported that students expressed concerns about potential risks, such as privacy, data security, and the authenticity of information generated by AI. Hlazunova et al. (2025) insist data privacy issues must be considered before these technologies can successfully be integrated into the learning process. In building an AI-powered SIS, the developers must employ privacy protection and data encryption to ensure student information security (Zhang, 2025; Alotaibi, 2024). Also to combat ethical and privacy when dealing with big data, Villegas-Ch et al. (2025) emphasized the need for data

anonymization strategies and the protection of sensitive information, highlighting that a lack of trust in data management can limit the adoption of these technologies. Mkinga and Mandari (2022) noted practical challenges in SIS, such as implementation costs, customization, and the evaluation of system quality. These challenges are particularly evident in developing countries where system availability and scalability remain critical (Mkinga & Mandari, 2022). Many universities in Nigeria struggled to implement the blended learning model envisioned by CCMAS due to infrastructural, ICT capacity deficit and pedagogical constraints (Alumona & Akinseinde, 2023; Okenema, 2025). Collectively, these findings underscore a need for national policy on ethical use of AI and data privacy in higher education and a call for action for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers.

Building a SIS may include a full range of data such as students’ academic records, Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA), LMS, payment platforms, schedules, timetable, which provides, real-time interaction and enhances the efficiency of education management (Wang et al., 2024). It is important for the SIS to be flexible to interoperate with external application to create an atmosphere that integrates students’ daily

management, teaching attendance, and cultural activities, while utilizing technological means to ensure student safety (Wu, 2024). In the Nigerian university system, Alumona and Akinseinde (2023) and Okenema (2025) opined that a rigid system with limited digital infrastructure hinders institutional goals of digitization and compliance with CCMAS e-Learning policy. With the help of intelligent analysis tools and APIs, challenges of interoperability can be mitigated to meet students’ needs, promotes personalized teaching and ensures multi-platform and multi-terminal access to realize the accessibility of information at anytime and anywhere (Wang et al., 2024; Villegas-Ch et al., 2025).

Research identified other notable gaps limiting technological advances in SIS in the context of Nigerian tertiary education ecosystem such as high cost of internet subscription, need for training staff and students, epileptic power supply among others (Alumona & Akinseinde, 2023). While literature on these gaps is inexhaustive, this study is limited to addressing aspects of leveraging AI for enhanced student productivity. The subsequent chapter details how Cubbes SIS addresses challenges of limited student engagement, data privacy, data integrity, algorithm bias and interoperability with external data and other third-party apps.

Table 1: Summary of relevant research findings

S/N	Author & Year	Title	Problem The Paper Addresses	Results & Findings	Journal Used
1	Yuskovych-Zhukovska et al. (2022)	Application of Artificial Intelligence in Education. Problems and Opportunities for Sustainable Development	Explores opportunities and risks of AI in education and its role in sustainable development.	Identifies both benefits and limitations of AI integration in learning systems.	BRAIN: Broad Research in Artificial Intelligence and Neuroscience, 13(1Sup1), 339–356
2	Zhang. (2025)	Construction of Artificial Intelligence-driven Education Management Informatization System and Its	Examines how AI-driven information systems can improve education quality monitoring and decision-making in universities.	Incorporates association rules and Apriori algorithm to enhance student learning and management efficiency.	Sciendo. Applied Mathematics and Nonlinear Sciences, 10(1) (2025) 1-18

3	Villegas-Ch et al. (2025)	Practice in College Management Adaptive intelligent tutoring systems for STEM education: analysis of the learning impact and effectiveness of personalized feedback	Proposes an AI-based intelligent tutoring system for real-time, adaptive learning experiences.	Experimental results show significant improvements in programming (85%) and mathematics (78%) performance; positive correlation between usage time and learning progress; 80% of students valued adaptive feedback.	Smart Learning Environments (2025) 12:41
4	Xieling Chen et al. (2022)	Two Decades of Artificial Intelligence in Education: Contributors, Collaborations, Research Topics, Challenges, and Future Directions	Notes challenges of instructor acceptance and reluctance to adopt AI in teaching. Focuses on data security and storage risks in AI-powered learning systems.	Concludes that lack of instructor experience hinders AI adoption; improved acceptance strategies needed. Finds that ML models may inadvertently store sensitive data; calls for stricter data protection measures.	Journal of Educational Technology & Society, 25(1), 28–47
5	Mukerjee (2012)	Student Information Systems – Implementation Challenges and the Road Ahead	Discusses challenges of implementing SIS in universities (cost, customization, scalability).	Reports on Australian universities' experiences; notes cost, resources, and adaptability as key challenges.	Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management, Vol. 34(1)
6	Mkinga and Mandari (2022)	Evaluating Student Information System Success	Few HLIs in Tanzania evaluate SIS effectiveness; study applies DeLone & McLean's Model.	System quality strongly affects use and effectiveness; recommends ensuring SIS availability 24/7.	International Information Management Association, Inc. (ISSN: 1941-6679)
7	Bhosale and Jamsandekar (2022)	Blockchain for Student Information System: Need of Technological Adoption	Examines need for blockchain to enhance SIS efficiency and security.	Finds blockchain improves data efficiency, security, and adoption through clustering and pattern recognition.	Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results, Vol. 13, Special Issue 6
8	Karoglou et al. (2025)	Building an Adaptive AI-Powered Higher Education Class for the Future of Engineering: A Case Study from NTUA	This study contributes significantly to higher education, particularly within engineering disciplines, by proposing a personalized and adaptive learning framework supported by artificial intelligence and virtual reality technologies	Students reported high satisfaction; findings show HECOF positively impacted learning outcomes, though improvement varied across individuals.	Applied Sciences, 15, 8524 (2025)

Conceptual Framework

In this study, we performed a conceptual analysis of SIS and reviewed the literature to track the framework and challenges, which formed the basis for the implementation of an AI-based approach to enhance the subject matter. Proper analysis helped to avoid repetition of research problem and to come up with novel concept and problem specification, review of literature tracks research gap and methodological gap which needs continuous improvement and adoption in framework such as adaptive learning (Villegas-Ch et al., 2025; Karoglou et al., 2025; Alwakid et al., 2025), quality monitoring (Zhang, 2025), and data

security (Chen et al., 2022; Bhosale and Jamsandekar, 2022). The proposed framework simplifies and improves the cohesive model for SIS improvement.

The proposed framework emphasizes three key dimensions:

- a) Engagement and Personalization: Data mining algorithms are used to improve clustering and decision making. Association rules and the apriori algorithm can significantly improve both learning support and institutional efficiency. Predictive analytics for student attrition, performance, and resource allocation. Automated summarization of course materials

and generation of study insights. Recommender systems for learning content, past questions, and productivity tools. Personalized dashboards based on academic history, Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) calculators, progress, and learning patterns. Adaptive course recommendations are aligned with student learning needs.

- b) Data Privacy, Data Security, Algorithm Bias: Biometric or multifactor authentication for student identity verification. Leveraging AI to ensure secure and transparent management of academic records. Cubbes administrator cross-checks integrity of contribution made by students. Algorithm bias is taken care of through multiple data training, diverse data

integration including the CCMAS, human oversight, fairness testing, transparency, user feedback, and compliance with ethical guidelines.

- c) Interoperability: API-driven integration with institutional LMS, digital libraries, proctoring software, plagiarism checkers, PayPal, Remita, JupyterLab, MATLAB & Simulink, and other productivity platforms etc. Data exchange with institutional systems such as admissions, finance, networking, social media, Student Affairs, student mentorship, etc. for holistic student support. Seamless connectivity with communication and collaboration tools such as chatbots, forums, and virtual classrooms.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of Cubbes AI-Powered SIS

The framework positions Cubbes as a cloud-based platform that ingests multiple inputs, including CCMAS, past questions, course material, text, video, audio and other unstructured data and processes them through AI-driven functionalities. The LMS is a subset of the SIS. The LMS is a software application hosted and provided by the University for the purpose of delivering, managing, and tracking educational courses, training programs, or learning activities online. It is the responsibility of the university to upload course materials

including the 30 percent-specific content unique to the institution, in line with the CCMAS. The Cubbes SIS then selectively retrieves data that is personalized for the student.

Methodology

Architecture of AI-Powered Student Information System

According to Ouyang and Xu (2024), an SIS architecture is a modular architecture that incorporates multiple AI components to facilitate adaptive and personalized learning

experiences. The Cubbes system architecture is a hub where various types of academic data (unstructured student data, CCMAS, past exam questions, lecture notes, slides, multimedia resources - audio, video, images) are processed via AI pipelines to create personalised learning, authenticated records, and interoperability with other digital applications.

Laravel Framework was used for backend development for modularity, scalability, and maintainability. PHP was used as the server-side programming language to implement the logic, user requests, data flow and secure communication between modules. DigitalOcean Cloud Infrastructure was utilised to provide hosting, reliability, scalability, and security for the services. Some of the AI capabilities include Natural Language Processing (NLP) for summarization and conversational support, recommendation algorithms for study resources, clustering models for content categorization, and predictive analytics for student performance tracking.

Figure 2: Live Screenshot of Basic (left) and Premium (right) Features of the Cubbes

App Evaluation & Data Collection

The Cubbes application was evaluated using a mixed-method approach. Quantitative data were obtained using app analytics including download counts, active

sessions, feature usage and an online survey. Qualitative insights were obtained from open-ended responses and follow-up interviews with students. Undergraduate and postgraduate students from both STEM and non-STEM disciplines across public and private universities. The selection was intended to ensure diversity in academic backgrounds, institutional types, and learning needs. 184 students across 170 universities, including Federal, State and Private were selected as respondents using a stratified random sampling technique. As at the time of data collection, the number of universities in Nigeria was numbered at 298 (NUC,2025) and the number onboarded universities on the Cubbes platform was numbered at 170 (Cubbes.app, 2025). The evaluation included the adoption of the application, efficiency, and satisfaction, which were carried out using a survey, usage logs, and performance indicators.

Procedure

- Development of the Cubbes SIS was carried out using the described architecture and technical stack of Laravel Framework, PHP and NLP.
- Deployment of the application on DigitalOcean for student access.
- Recruitment of student participants across diverse universities.
- Selection of educators and student champions for quality assurance, data integrity and human oversight.
- Orientation of participants on app usage.
- For the study, data were collected through system logs, questionnaires, and interviews, over a period of five weeks, between July - August 2025.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Analysis: Data were analysed using Mean, Standard Deviation Independent samples t-test. The survey was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

The mean was used to summarize students’ overall ratings of Cubbes features, while the standard deviation measured the spread of responses and consistency across participants. To compare differences between groups, the independent samples t-test was applied. This allowed us to determine whether observed differences in satisfaction, engagement, or trust in security features were statistically significant rather than due to chance.

Qualitative Analysis: NVivo was used to analyse the open-ended responses. The transcripts were cleaned, anonymized, and imported into NVivo, where both deductive and inductive coding were applied. Key nodes included student engagement, productivity, security, and personalization. NVivo queries such as word frequency and matrix coding helped identify recurring patterns, while visualizations highlighted dominant perspectives. Thematic insights were then triangulated with quantitative results, ensuring a robust and credible interpretation of findings.

Result

The deployment of Cubbes (<https://cubbes.app/>) has shown encouraging adoption and measurable impacts across Nigerian universities. As of August 2025, the following metrics was used to evaluate the platform:

Table 2: Overall Metrics of Cubbes SIS

Metric	Value (as of August 2025)
Institutions onboarded	170
Courses uploaded	37,640+
Study resources (lecture notes, past questions, multimedia content)	250,000+
Registered students	45,722+

Active Usage	62% of the downloaders became active monthly users (~9,300 students)
Engagement	Average of 3.4 sessions per week per user, with spikes during exam periods
Top Features Accessed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course materials (78%) • Past questions (65%) • Productivity tools (48%) • Collaboration features (31%)

In addition, the application has achieved over 45,000 downloads across PlayStore and AppStore, demonstrating traction beyond early adopters (Cubbes, 2025).

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Students’ Perceptions of Cubbes SIS (N = 184)

Construct	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Ease of Use	4.2	0.6
Personalization of Content	4.0	0.7
Efficiency in Study Preparation	4.3	0.5
Trust in Security & Authentication	3.7	0.9
Engagement	3.7	0.9
Overall Satisfaction	4.1	0.6

Table 4: Independent Samples t-Test Results for Student Perceptions

Variable	Group Comparison	Mean Difference	t(df)	p-value
Gender (Male vs. Female)	No significant difference	0.05	0.84(182)	.401
University Type (Public vs. Private)	Federal (M=4.2) > Private (M=3.9)	0.3	2.15(182)	.033*

*Note. *p < .05 indicates significance.

Table 5: Adoption Metrics of Cubbes SIS (N = 184)

benefits of features like time management features e.g. reminder of upcoming deadlines, smart scheduling, and performance tracking, which assisted in reducing stress, maintaining motivation, and managing their time effectively between school and other commitments. By balancing the demands of part-time work with academic responsibilities, using automated scheduling tools and a CGPA calculator helped clarify respondents' performance. These results were in line with the objectives of the NUC CCMAS e-Learning guidelines which promotes learner-centred learning by providing digital resources to the learners (NUC, 2023).

RQ2: How do students and educators address data privacy and algorithm biases in use of AI-powered SIS?

The analysis showed that students and educators viewed issues of data privacy and algorithm bias as critical issues in adopting AI-powered SIS. Nevertheless, respondents on the survey felt quite confident in the security and authentication processes of Cubbes (Mean = 3.7, SD = 0.9), with multi-factor authentication and document verification assurance for sensitive academic records being facilitated by the system's capabilities. From the qualitative data analysed in NVivo, the importance of transparent communication on student data collection, storage, and use was highlighted by participants. Regular system updates and privacy notices were appreciated. Similarly, Wang et al. (2024) reported that in a survey on impact of AI application in personalized learning environments, students highlighted privacy and ethical issues, expressing concerns about the potential risks to personal privacy and data security associated with using AI tools. Cubbes was scored positively for incorporating feedback loops in which

student champions, educators and subject expert could report suspicious outputs, minimising the notion of algorithm bias. It is clear from these discussions that academics felt that it was important for institutional regulation for universities to be seen as a complement to Cubbes' inherent protections and for national regulation on ethical ways that AI can be used.

Independent Samples t-Test

The t-test showed no significant gender difference in perceptions regarding Cubbes SIS ($p = .401$) indicating that both male and female students perceive the system in a similar fashion. However, there was a significant difference between those attending public and private universities ($p = .033$) with public students more favourable in their assessment of the system ($M = 4.2$ vs. 3.9). This suggests that the nature of the institution affects student perceptions, with federal universities posting higher valuing of the system given relatively large class sizes and shortfalls in resources to address this.

Interoperability

Villegas-Ch et al. (2025) mentioned that it is essential for the AI-SIS design to present a reproducible framework for scalable, interoperable, and ethically aligned systems along with flexibility for different curricula and platforms. Findings from this study showed that students are able to upload past questions, course materials and able to access existing learning content on the Cubbes SIS. These findings were supported in qualitative interviews. Students frequently emphasized the convenience of integrating multiple learning resources, including course materials, past questions, and notes into a single application. "Instead of going from portal to portal, everything's centralised in one place, and it even says to me, this is the

one thing you need to work on next," says one student. Table 2 showed that the least used feature, Collaboration Features, was at 31%. This suggests that despite the value of these third-party tools (Payment), they are not fully exploited because of factors such as lack of technological resource and digital literacy, to name a few.

Limitations and Challenges

Alumona and Akinseinde (2023) have enumerated some of the challenges in the adoption of SIS as high cost of internet subscription, need for training or retraining of staff members and students, epileptic power supply among others. Cubbes SIS can only deal with selected areas of using AI for better student productivity. Despite the positive aspects of the application, this study has identified some challenges in using the application. Some respondents of the open-ended survey cited cost of data as one of their major impediments to accessing the internet to use the app, particularly off campus. Some users complained of inability to find past questions and course material for some courses. In addition, while Cubbes was designed to accommodate third-party apps, challenge of bureaucracy in obtaining APIs to integrating services like requesting results and transcripts from the university portals was reported. In terms of security of the app, some users worried about long-term data privacy, and recommended the need of effective cybersecurity and national compliance practices.

Conclusion

This research has shown how the use of AI SIS can greatly benefit and change the student experience and institutional practises in Nigerian universities. Using Cubbes as an example, both quantitative and qualitative studies showed that AI-powered features like

adaptive assists, personalised student experiences, verified academic course contents, and productivity tools increase student engagement, decrease academic stress, and drive personalization pathways. Successful implementation in various universities affirm that Cubbes is a scalable and inclusive platform with quantifiable impact in terms of efficiency, satisfaction and compliance towards the NUC's CCMAS e-Learning policy. Importantly, the study also brought up important considerations regarding data privacy, security, and algorithmic bias, emphasizing the need for a balance between technological advancement and ethical considerations. Results show that open design, mixed data training, and multi-tiers of authentication are important for ongoing adoption.

Future Development

The interoperability challenges of AI-SIS indicated in this study suggest that national-level coordination, similar to the HECOF initiative described by Karoglou et al. (2025) on building on existing adaptive learning models and architecture, educational psychology, and following ethical AI guidelines, will be crucial for future developments. This supports the work of Hlazunova et al. (2025), who insist that data privacy issues must be considered before these technologies can successfully be integrated into new learning processes. Furthermore, Bhosale and Jamsandekar (2022) suggested blockchain based SIS solutions to resolve security, efficiency, and authentication issues, but undoubtedly such solutions are experimental.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were given:

- i. Researchers, practitioners, and policymakers should develop a national policy guiding the ethical use of AI and data privacy for higher education.

- ii. Students are encouraged to adopt usage of AI-Powered SIS to enhance their productivity on academic and extra-curricular activities.
- iii. Universities should invest in digital infrastructure, provide regular digital literacy for staff and students and comply with existing CCMAS e-Learning guidelines.

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